

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

D3 - Report describing the fixed-point cells (Al (660.323 °C), Ag (961.78 °C), Cu (1084.62 °C), Fe-C (1154 °C), Co-C (1324.24 °C), Pd-C (1492 °C), Pt-C (1738.28 °C) and Re-C (2474.69 °C)) constructed in the project, the results of the characterisation measurements and a summary of the optimisation processes. The target uncertainty in the practical realisation of the transition temperature is less than 0.6 °C (k=2)

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP

Glossary

Eutectic – Here a mixture of metal and carbon in a ratio so that the melting point is minimised.
FP - Fixed-point, graphite crucible filled with metal/metal-carbon that has a fixed melting/freezing temperature.

NMI – National Metrology Institute

DI – Designated institute

POI - Point of Inflection

SSE – Size of Source Effect

ITS-90 - International temperature scale of 1990

MeP-K - Mise-en-pratique, or best practice, for the realisation of the kelvin

Fixed-points and shielding gas

Al – Aluminium, 660.323 °C

Ag – Silver, 961.78 °C

Au – Gold, 1064.18 °C

Cu – Copper, 1084.62 °C

Fe-C – Iron-carbon, 1154 °C

Co-C – Cobalt-carbon, 1324.24 °C

Pd-C – Palladium-Carbon, 1492 °C

Pt-C – Platinum-Carbon, 1738.28 °C

Re-C – Rhenium-Carbon, 2474.69 °C

Ar – Argon

NMIs and DIs

RISE – Sweden, Research institutes of Sweden AB

JV – Norway, Justervesenet

LNE – France, Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais

CNAM – France, Conservatoire national des arts et métiers

SMU – Slovakia, Slovenský Metrologický Ústav

CMI – Czechia, Český Metrologický Institut

UL – Slovenia, Univerza v Ljubljani

TUBITAK – Türkiye, Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Arastirma Kurumu

DFM – Denmark, Dansk Fundamental Metrologi A/S

DTU – Denmark, Danmarks Tekniske Universitet

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1 Summary

This report describes the manufacturing of high temperature fixed-point cells (Al, Ag, Au, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C, Pt-C and Re-C) in the project MultiFixRad. The fixed points include both conventional cells with pure metal, as well as eutectic cells with a metal-carbon mixture. The report also includes the results of the characterisation measurements and the optimisation processes. Seven NMIs (JV, RISE, CMI, SMU, UL, TUBITAK and DFM/DTU), with the additional help of LNE-CNAM, planned to fill a total of 28 high temperature fixed-point cells in the project, but several more were eventually made.

The fixed point cells are of a hybrid design based on cells developed, and previously used, at LNE-CNAM and were manufactured using graphite of high purity and density. The cells were designed to be filled with the piston method, where during the last melting a piston is pushed down into the extension that is screwed on to the crucible. The extension allows more metal or metal-carbon mixture to be added during each melt. When the piston is pushed down it helps the cell in filling completely, while any excess will be pressed into the piston and can be used for analysis of impurities.

The metals used in the project were acquired by the individual NMIs and were of a purity of 99.99% or better. It came as either a powder or in small bits. The carbon used was in powder form, and about 3% by weight was used in the metal-carbon mixture. For the eutectic cells, the metal and carbon were mixed before it was added to the crucibles. The large size difference between the metal bits and the graphite powder made the mixing difficult in some cases.

Due to the design with the added extension, it was possible to fill most of the pure metal cells in only one or two melts. When metal in powder form was used it required more melts due to the low density. There were no reports of the cell breaking during filling, and generally the filling process went well. Some of the problems reported included metal leaking outside the crucible, difficulties removing the extension and incorrect carbon contents in the mixture. The problems related to a stuck extension and piston had to do with the metal alloying itself with the carbon in the graphite, thereby acting as a glue and leading to the extension having to be cut off with a saw. The incorrect carbon contents were in the case of the Pd-C fixed points and resulted in an ingot that had not melted properly and had the wrong composition. The reason was an excess of carbon, and it resulted in the cells needing to be remade because they did not fill properly and did not contain enough of the metal-carbon mixture.

Before the fixed-point cells could be properly used, they had to be optimized in terms of the positioning in the furnace, the ramp speed and the set-points on the furnace. This was done by measuring the temperature gradients in the furnace and positioning the cell where they were as small as possible. The optimal furnace set-points and ramp speed was found by trial and error, where it was changed until the melting plateau was as long and well defined as possible.

During usage of the fixed points there were some issues, although they mostly worked as expected. A few of the cells have cracked and broken during usage for varying, sometimes unknown reasons. Two Co-C and one Re-C cell had the same issues with a badly defined melting plateau and an unusually low melting temperature. The metal for all three cells was specified to be 99.99% purity, but it is likely that the problems were caused by impurities. None of the metal in these cells have been sent off for analysis, so it is not yet known for sure if this is the reason and in that case what impurity caused it.

2 Background

Following the recent redefinition of the kelvin, the *mise-en-pratique* of the new definition (*MeP-K*)¹ offers new possibilities to realise and disseminate thermodynamic temperature using multiple high-temperature fixed points. This is one of the most promising primary reference standards for high temperature and uses a radiation thermometer as the interpolation instrument to interpolate between the high temperature fixed points, whose transition temperatures have been established with high accuracy. However, the method has not yet been implemented on a large scale outside the major NMIs. An important pillar of the metrological community is the ability to compare results across different institutions and countries, but this requires that a certain number of institutes are capable of realising the quantity to be compared. To address these aims some less experienced NMIs/DIs need to develop primary thermometry capabilities, including the ability to construct, characterise, use and maintain fixed points intended for radiometric applications, and to establish a primary temperature scale in line with the revised MeP-K.

This work has been part of the project MultiFixRad and aims to assist 6 less experienced European national metrology institutes and designated institutes (JV, RISE, DFM, CMI, SMU, and UL) in establishing their own primary reference scales for thermometry using this approach. One of the objectives of the project is to construct a set of medium- to high-temperature fixed points for radiation thermometry adapted to the technical means of less experienced NMIs/DIs. This includes assessment of the quality of the cells and experimental determination of the optimal thermal conditions for their use. In addition to the 6 less experienced NMIs, this report also describes the fixed-point cells manufactured and realised at TUBITAK, one of the more experienced NMIs in the project.

The improved high-temperature measurement standards will respond to industrial needs in the countries and enable participation in development projects for fundamental thermometry at high temperature, and at the highest scientific level.

In addition to the previously mentioned NMIs, the experienced NMI LNE-CNAM has also been parts of the MultiFixRad project, and has been particularly involved in the design, manufacture and realisation of the fixed-point cells described in this report.

3 Introduction

3.1 Design

The design of the fixed-point cells can be seen in Figure 1 and was made by LNE-CNAM. It was based on a design that has been developed at LNE-CNAM during several years and projects. The cell consists of five parts (01 Crucible, 02 Cavity, 03 Sleeve, 04 Ring, 05 Cap), as well as some graphite foil. For filling the cells an additional four parts are used (06 Extension, 07 Piston, 08 Stopper, 09 Stick). The drawings for the graphite parts are available in Appendix A.

All parts of the cells are made from pure graphite, and the cells are filled with either a pure metal or a eutectic metal-carbide mixture. The graphite parts were ordered as one large order from SGL carbon and were manufactured from SIGRAFINE R6710P5 with a bulk density of 1.88 g/cm³ and high purity. The metal and carbon powder were acquired by the individual NMIs from different sources.

¹ Available on the BIPM web pages, last visited June 2026: https://www.bipm.org/documents/d/guest/mep-k-relative_primary_radiometry

Figure 1: Design of a filled fixed-point on the right and the setup for filling the crucible on the left.

The NMIs in the project aimed at filling a total of 28 fixed-point cells, although several more had been manufactured by the end of the project.

3.2 Eutectic fixed-points

A conventional fixed-point cell consists of a pure metal in a crucible. The crucible is made of a material that can withstand the melting temperature of the metal and not contaminate the metal. At higher temperatures it is difficult to find a suitable material for the crucibles. A solution to this is eutectic fixed-points, where a eutectic mixture of a metal and carbon is filled in a graphite crucible. A eutectic mixture is a mixture of two elements with the ratio of each that results in lowest melting temperature. For the metal-carbon mixtures used here it is generally about 3% carbon by weight. The advantage of this ratio is that any excess carbon will fall out of the solution, while a deficit results in a small amount of carbon from the crucible being dissolved into the metal.

3.3 Filling

Instructions for filling the graphite crucibles with metal or a metal-carbon mixture can be found in appendix B “Guide to filling high temperature fixed points” by Frédéric Bourson at Laboratoire de Métrologie LNE-Cnam (2023).

The guide presents the techniques for filling metal-carbon fixed-point cells using the piston method. In this method an extension is screwed onto the crucible and is used to be able to add more of the metal than would otherwise fit in the crucible. This is necessary because the metal often comes as a powder or small shots, that takes up much more space than the final solid metal. As the metal melts in the furnace, it flows from the

extension into the crucible. Any remaining metal in the extension is pressed down using a piston. Using this method, it is possible to fill a fixed-point cell in a few fillings. During the last filling the ring is added. Any excess metal will be pushed through the hole in the ring, as the piston is pressed down, and will flow into the extension. This metal plug can be used as a sample for future chemical analysis of the metal. After the filling the cap is added to the crucible and the fixed-point is completed.

4 Fixed-point cell construction

The sections below describe the filling of the fixed-point cells at the different NMIs as part of the work in the MultiFixRad project. The final types and number of cells filled by each NMI can be seen in Table 1 below.

	CMI	DFM/DTU	JV	RISE	SMU	TUBITAK	UL
Al		2	1				
Ag			1	1	1		
Au					1		
Cu			1	2	2	3	1
Fe-C			1	1	1	2	1
Co-C	1	2	1	1	2	1	1
Pd-C	1	1	1	1	2		1
Pt-C			2				
Re-C	2			1			

Table 1: Number and type of cells made by each NMI in the project.

4.1 CMI

CMI has created 4 cells within the project, 1 Co-C, 1 Pd-C and 2 Re-C cells. Due to the breakage of the filling furnace, only Co-C was filled in the CMI facility. Pd-C and Re-C were filled in June 2025 in LNE CNAMs facilities.

The Co-C cell was filled with the step method (11 steps), the others were filled with the piston method in two steps. Material used for filling is listed in Table 2 along with the purity. Table 3 shows the weight of the pure material used to create the eutectic cells, along with the amount that was left over after the cell was full.

Substance	Form	Purity
Co	Powder	99.9999 %
Pd	Powder	99.99 %
Re	Slices	99.99 %
C	Powder	99.9995 %
C-C Sheets,	Textile	better than 10 ppm

Table 2: Overview of materials used by CMI.

Cell	Mass metal	Mass C	Residual material
Co-C	29.09 g	0.48 g	-
Pd-C	36.9 g	0.63 g	4,8
Re-C1	68.9 g	0.35 g	9,015
Re-C2	69.76 g	0.35 g	8,341

Table 3: Core data from the first ingot melting with CMI cells.

Co-C

In the case of the Co-C cell, a special inductive equipment was used for filling. This device is strictly used for fixed point cells up to Co-C fixed point cells. This cell was not filled using the piston method as the other cells.

Figure 2: Co-C cell filled with a mixture of cobalt and carbon powder.

The fixed-point was inserted filled with a “raw” powder mixture (Figure 2) and heated to a temperature just below the melting point. Then melting of the mixture was then induced by setting the temperature in the device approx. 50 °C above the expected melting point. To be sure of a sufficient melt of the mixture the fixed point was left at the elevated temperature for approximately 30 minutes. The cooling process of the whole system was then initialised, and another filling was possible after the cell cooled down to ambient temperature. One filling cycle took approximately 4 hours. After 11 steps the cell was filled completely. At the back of the cell, two layers of the C-C sheet were placed, and the cell was closed with an end cap. Photos from the manufacturing process can be seen in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Co-C fixed point cell during manufacturing process.

One **Pd-C** and two of **Re-C** cell were filled at LNE-CANM with the use of the piston method. After the crucible was assembled with the other parts, the extension tube was installed on the cell and approximately half of the prepared metal-carbon mixture was filled in the crucible and extension. A photo of the rhenium metal and carbon powder can be seen in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Prepared mixture of the Re slices and C powder for filling the cell with the piston method

The whole setup was then installed in the HTBB furnace, and a first melt of the mixture was realised. After the crucible had cooled down the second part of the mixture was filled in the crucible and extension tube and finally the piston was inserted into the extension in order to finish the cell filling during the second melting cycle. After reaching the expected temperature necessary for melting the metal-carbon mix, the piston was slightly pushed down to let the redundant part of the mixture migrate into the piston part. In order to prevent even the slightest uplift of the piston, due to the internal pressure, constant pressure was applied to the top of the piston during the cooling process. Then the extension was cut from the crucible, 2 layers of C-C sheets were put under the cap and cells were closed. Photos from the filling of the Pd-C and Re-C fixed-point cells can be seen below (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

Figure 5: Pd-C fixed point filling at LNE-Cnam facility

Figure 6: Process of Re-C fixed point filling.

4.2 DFM/DTU

The partners DFM and DTU collaborated on the creation and realization of fixed points. DTU created 2 Co-C fixpoints, DFM created one Pd-C fixpoint and an Al fixpoint. In the following text the work from both institutes will be described as one.

A cell melting setup was created for constructing fixed points as well as for other uses in the future. This entailed the construction of a single zone furnace using high temperature insulation and MoS₂ heating elements, enabling heating to above 1600 °C. An alumina tube was positioned in the centre, standing on insulation at the bottom. The limitation for this furnace is the heating elements, that are rated for 1800°C.

The filling procedure and the insertion of the filling cell in the constructed vertical MoS₂ oven is shown in Figure 7.

A custom fixpoint holder was fabricated to enable the stepwise melting and assembly of the fixed points. A closed bottom alumina cylinder was fashioned and the fixed-point crucible lowered down. A small hole was drilled in the bottom of the alumina holder to allow Ar gas to flow from below, ensuring an oxygen free environment for the fixed-point. A lip was glued to the tube using a high temperature ceramic bonding agent and a thermocouple was attached to the outside of the tube using the same agent. This enabled the fine temperature control of the furnace for the melting and freezing stages of the fixpoint assembly. The temperature control showed a fine control of better than < 0.2 °C. The thermocouple was never calibrated as it was not necessary nor feasible in the alumina holder.

Figure 7: DFM/DTU filling procedure and vertical MoS2 oven.

The procedure for assembling the fixed points described in Appendix B were followed.

Co-C

Manufacturing the Co-C fixed-point cell involved some difficulties because of the different graphite sheets used, with the material thickness of 0.25 mm being more brittle compared to the initial graphite mesh sheet used.

Another difficulty was that the Cobalt powder tended to clump together and took significantly more steps to finish. Eventually a harder press of the piston resulted in a good filling level. Two Co-C fixed points were created using comparable methods.

The ratio of material used was that determined by JV based on their experience

Pd-C

The palladium-carbon fixed-point cell was produced in accordance with the procedure given by LNE-CNAM. The material used was palladium powder with a purity of 99.99%.

Al

In addition to the planned fixpoints, an aluminium fixed-point was created using aluminium pellets with a purity of 99.999%. The standard procedure was followed, and the resulting fixed-point cell appeared fine, although it has yet to be tested.

4.3 JV

Justervesenet created a setup for cell melting to fit inside an existing furnace, an Isotech 465 three-zone furnace. Its upper operational temperature is 1200 °C. The setup is shown in Figure 8, a quartz tube is sealed at the top using a special head with a gas feed-through to connect a vacuum system and Ar gas supply. Inside the tube a set of insulation bricks is used to raise the cell to approximately the centre of the heated region. The cell is assembled, with extender, and placed appropriately, before filling the void with insulation and attaching the seal to the top of the quartz tube.

Figure 8: Melt setup at Justervesenet. Left: the top seal attached to the quartz tube. The graphite rod, attached to the piston, is seen emerging from the white insulation wool, and the solid steel extension rod that is fed through the seal to enable a mechanical pressure on the melt. Centre: the cell, extender and piston mounted inside the quartz tube. The graphite rod used to push the piston down extends from the top into the white insulation. Right: The entire assembly removed from the furnace with a silver cell that has been melted and cooled below the freezing temperature.

The graphite sheets used between the sleeve and the crucible wall were as specified in Table 4 below. This gap is around 1.25 mm and initially three individual pieces of thickness 0.5 mm, 0.5 mm and 0.25 mm were carefully cut and wrapped around the sleeve. A simpler method was later adopted in which a long piece of 0.25 mm thickness was rolled around the sleeve 5 times.

The ingot materials were weighed and mixed before being put inside the extension tube. The purity and form of the metals used by JV is shown in Table 4. For powders the filling had to be done in more than one step. In those cases, the piston and end cap were not installed until the final filling.

Substance	Form	Purity
Al	Pellet	>99.995 %
Ag	Pellet	99.99 %
Cu	Pellet	99.99 %
Fe	Pellet	99.99 %
Co	Powder	99.99 %
Pd	Powder	99.99 %
Pt	Powder	99.99 %
C	Powder	99.998 %
C Sheets, Sigraflex from SGL Carbon.	Paper, 0.25 mm/0.50 mm/0.75 mm	

Table 4: Overview of materials used by JV.

For the cells with Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C and Pt-C the melting temperature is close to or above the upper temperature limit of the furnace available at JV. Those cells were instead melted at the facilities of RISE. During the project JV personnel have visited RISE on 4 occasions to produce cells. This is one clear example of the enhanced collaboration fostered by the project and serves as an example of regional specialisation.

Cell	Mass metal	Mass C	Residual material
Al	22.05 g	-	~11 g
Ag	See text	-	
Cu	34.837 g	-	6.572 g
Fe-C	30.01 g	0.86 g	
Co-C	30.04 g	0.74 g	4.79 g
Pd-C	45.00 g	1.50 g	See text
Pt-C	79.00 g	0.00 g	14.94 g

Table 5: Core data from the first ingot melting with JV cells.

Ag

The silver cell was the first cell constructed at JV and served as a test case for the ingot melting setup. While the cell itself seems to behave as expected (see later section on the realisation of phase transitions for calibration), the first experiment highlighted a few necessary improvements to both the procedure followed and the head seal. Firstly, no detailed record was written on the composition of the cell. We observed a moderate amount of residual material but did not weigh it. Secondly, after the first ingot melting, we allowed the cell to cool slowly to some °C below freezing and then removed the cell fast from the furnace. Provided that the ingot was completely frozen this procedure is unlikely to influence the next melting, but the setup does not cater for a separate temperature probe to verify the temperature in the ingot itself: hence, the decision to remove the cell from the furnace is taken based on the furnace control temperature, which does not show the freeze process and is an unreliable measure of the state of the ingot phase. In later ingot melts we left the setup to cool naturally inside the furnace. Lastly, we observed a substantial erosion of the upper part of the piston tube when the assembly was recovered. While no detailed examination was performed, we concluded that the likely explanation was the presence of oxygen in the system which reacted with the graphite at high temperatures. No damage was observed on the crucible however, but the seal head was redesigned to improve the atmosphere control.

Al

The aluminium cell was prepared with around twice the necessary amount of metal. Apart from that the cell appears to be fully usable. However, currently JV lacks a suitable radiometer to measure the plateau and will not be able to implement one before the end of the project.

Cu

The filling of the copper cell was successful on the first attempt and has since been characterised with JVs radiometer.

Fe-C

For the iron-carbon fixed-point cell the metal-carbon composition was taken from the guidance document of LNE. The Fe metal forms the eutectic composition easily and readily dissolves available carbon, also from the crucible parts if not enough C powder is mixed in initially.

Co-C

The cobalt-carbon fixed-point cell was filled with a metal-carbon mixture as in the guidance document and was likewise melted in accordance with standard procedure.

Pt-C

In platinum-carbon the eutectic composition has a fairly small mass-fraction of carbon. During cell construction no additional C was added to the ingot mixture, instead the carbon was supplied by the graphite crucible. Two cells were constructed in the same way, and they both appeared to be as expected. However, they have not been tested with a radiometer.

Pd-C

The palladium-carbon cell turned out to be more challenging. The result of the first ingot melt is shown in Figure 9. The Pd and C mixture was inadvertently prepared with an excess of carbon. After unmounting the extension tube the upper part of the ingot consisted of powder that could be brushed away. Inside the piston a large uniform slab of material had formed after pushing the piston down while the ingot material was melted. When extracting the ingot from the crucible we observed a very irregular and incomplete ingot. It seemed that most of the eutectic has collected above the crucible and was unable to flow down into it. This situation persisted even after repeating the melt by first refitting the extension tube, then placing the residual material directly on top of the blackbody wall and refitting the piston on top. An interesting detail in the centre picture of Figure 9 is the curved shape of the free surface. It curves upwards near the piston wall, at a large angle, which suggests that the liquid eutectic has a high surface tension and is non-wetting on graphite surfaces.

Figure 9: Left: the top of the crucible after 2 melts. The material at the top of the crucible was almost powder-like and easy to brush off. Centre: the remaining material in the piston after 2 melts. The mass is around 25 g, or roughly half the amount used. Right: the ingot removed from the crucible, revealing large holes.

The observations suggest that somehow an agglomeration of carbon powder at the top of the crucible impedes the flow of the eutectic melt into the crucible. The reason that C is segregated is probably that we used excess amounts, however it is not clear why the C seems to collect near the top of the crucible. However, once it does, it is not unreasonable that the non-wetting, high surface tension fluid cannot flow through a layer of powder. The pressure we apply to the piston is not enough to overcome the flow impediment.

For the third attempt we used new components, placed the surplus material from the piston at the bottom of the extension tube, and material retrieved from the (poor quality) ingot on top, and redid the melting. The mass of the ingot was much closer to the expected after this attempt, but a further melt was carried out with a little added fresh material. The ingot then weighed a little under 38 g, which was considered satisfactory. Later use of the cell also suggests that the ingot is of reasonable quality.

The main lesson was to adjust the initial amount of C. Table 5 contains the updated starting mass for Pd-C cells with the current dimensions.

4.4 RISE

All fixed-point cells were filled using two furnaces, one Elite (Ag, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C and Pd-C) and one Thermo Gauge (Cu, Re-C). The graphite cell parts were used as they were delivered, with no modification, except for removing a sharp edge inside the lid to be able to tighten it all the way. For the Elite furnace a graphite extension was added to the stick to make it longer. The graphite foil used for wrapping the sleeve is 0.2 mm high purity Permafoil from Toyo Tanso. This was also used inside the lid, together with 0.5 mm woven graphite (CFC). The graphite powder used in the cells were high purity 99.9999% (6n) from Alfa Aesar with 200 mesh particle size.

The crucibles were filled inside an acrylic dust hood to reduce the risk of air born contaminants. All non-disposable tools and containers were cleaned between uses with ethanol. All metals were kept in sealed containers before and after use.

Ag

One silver cell has been manufactured at RISE. The cell was initially filled in two fillings using 3 mm Ag shots from Merck Life Science (Sigma-Aldrich) with a purity of 99.999% (5n). The measured final weight was lower (4 g) than expected and there was also a void in the top of the cell, see Figure 10. To try to correct this, an additional 3 melts were made using an additional 5 g of silver each time. Unfortunately, the void remained, and it was decided to leave it there and see later if it affected the plateau. This void was probably caused by the shrinkage of the metal as it cooled down.

Figure 10: Silver cell with a void.

Cu

Two copper cells have been manufactured at RISE using 6.35 mm shots with a purity of 99.99998% (6n8) from Merck Life Science (Sigma-Aldrich). The first one was made in the Elite furnace, and all the metal was added at the same time. For an unknown reason about 4 g of copper ended up between the disc and the piston (Figure 11), in addition to 7 g in the sample. This resulted in material missing in the cell which required an additional melt with more copper to completely fill it.

Figure 11: Copper cell (without the sleeve and crucible) with a disc of copper that have leaked out.

A second cell was made in the (newly installed) Thermo Gauge furnace to test it before it was used for filling the Re-C fixed-point. This cell was filled using two melts, with about half of the metal in each. During the second melt, the disc probably got stuck and was not pushed all the way down (3 mm left). A third melt was therefore required to push it down to the final position.

Fe-C

One iron-carbon fixed-point has been manufactured using 4 mm max. size cylindrical shots, with a purity of over 99.99% (4n) from Merck Life Science (Sigma-Aldrich). The shots were too large to fit in between the cavity and sleeve and did not mix well with the graphite powder. It was therefore decided to try to melt the metal/carbon mixture in the extension and during a second melt transfer it into the crucible. This was done by placing two layers of graphite foil between the crucible and extension and filling all the metal and carbon in the extension. After one melt the iron-carbon mixture had dissolved the graphite foil and flowed into the crucible. The disc and piston were therefore added and could be pushed down during a second melt. After it had cooled down it was noted that the extension had cracked just above the threaded part.

Co-C

One cobalt-carbon fixed-point cell was made using a mixture of 2 mm cubes with a purity of 99.999% (5n) from JX Nippon Mining & Metals, cobalt powder with a purity of 99.998% (4n8) from Alfa Aesar and graphite powder. The mixture of cubes and powder made for a mixture that was easier to make homogeneous than just using graphite powder and the cobalt cubes. 4 g of powder and about 28 g of cubes were used in the mixture. The fixed-point cell was filled with all the metal-carbon mixture in one melt and there were no noticeable problems.

Pd-C

One palladium-carbon fixed-point cell was made using palladium powder with a purity of 99.99% (4n) from Azelis and graphite powder. During the mixing of the two powders, it was noted that it was very difficult to achieve a homogeneous mixture. The reason could be because of the large difference in density between the two powders and that they seemed to not want to stick to each other, maybe due to the grain shape. An acceptable mixture was achieved after about 15 minutes of mixing, see Figure 12.

Figure 12: Mixture after several minutes of mixing. The graphite powder tended to float on top of the palladium.

During the first melt about 2/3 of the powder mixture was loaded in the crucible and extension. During the second melt the rest of the powder was added. During disassembly a larger than expected amount (11 g) of metal was found in the extension. When the cell was disassembled and the metal removed from the surrounding sleeve the surface was uneven and looked “dry” (see Figure 13) and parts of it was not properly melted.

Figure 13: Palladium-carbon after two melts. The surface is uneven and parts of it is not melted properly.

The most likely reason for the problems was an excess of carbon in the mixture. For the third melt a new cavity was mounted in the crucible as the old one was stuck to the previously melted metal. The sample from the previous melt, which looked to be properly melted, was placed in the extension and the old cavity was hung

upside-down in the top of the extension. Two melts were performed with this configuration, with an extended dwell time above the melting temperature, to ensure that all good material would melt and drip into the crucible. For the following melt, new metal-carbon powder was instead added. The graphite contents in this mixture were reduced from 1.7% to 0.7% by weight. After the melt the surface of the metal was inspected and found to be as expected. For the last melt the disk was added and the piston pressed down as described in the cell filling procedure.

After seven plateaus it was noticed that there was a small amount of metal in the cavity. The sleeve and cavity was therefore removed from the crucible, and more metal was found around the split between them. This was likely due to the cavity being inserted on a slight angle. A crack along the whole sleeve was also found, as seen in Figure 14 below.

Figure 14: Cracked sleeve in the Pd-C cell

It was therefore decided to remove the sleeve and remelt the metal-carbon into a new cell.

Re-C

One rhenium-carbon fixed point cell was made using 3-6 mm pieces of 99.99% (4n) purity rhenium from Testbourne and graphite powder. The crucible was mounted in the centre of the vertical unit of the Thermo Gauge furnace. This equipment is the same as the horizontal used for realizing the fixed-points, but is mounted on the outside of the furnace, with the pyrometer for the temperature control fixed under the graphite heating tube. To be able to place the crucible inside the tube three small holes were drilled and tapped under the centre of the tube and short threaded graphite rods were inserted in the holes for the crucible to stand on. To test the setup, an empty crucible was first placed in the tube and heated to 2550 °C. This crucible was then used for the Re-C fixed-point.

For the first melt slightly less than half of the material was filled in the cell and extension. During inspection after the melt, it was noted that part of the graphite in the crucible and extension had been eroded, signifying that the proportion of carbon probably should be increased above the 0.5% used here. For the second melt the rest of the material was added, as well as the disk and piston. After the second melt the extension had to be cut of the crucible using a saw, since a small amount of metal had leaked out where the extension had corroded, glueing them together.

4.5 SMU

The SMU has made 6 different fixed-point cells (1x Ag, 1x Au, 2x Cu, 1x Fe-C, 2x Co-C, 2x Pd-C) as can be seen in Table 6.

Fixed point	Name	Number of filling steps	Amount of metal material [g]	Amount of carbon [g]	FP mass [g]	Ingot mass [g]	Rest of material [g]
Cu	Cu1	2	33	x	53.8	28.2	4.8
Co-C	Co-C1	3	32	0.64	52.0	26.4	5.6
Cu	Cu2	2	32	x	53.6	28.1	3.9
Co-C	Co-C2	3	32	0.64	52.1	26.5	5.5
Pd-C	Pd-C1	1	44	1.36	54.5	29.0	15.1
Fe-C	Fe-C1	2	25	0.9	50.44	24.89	0.9
Au	Au1	2	70	x	86.66	60.56	9.44
Ag	Ag1	1	40	X	58.84	32.8	7.2
Pd-C	Pd-C2	2	37.9	0.66	54.51	28.9	9.66

Table 6 Summary of fixed-point cells manufactured at SMU.

The main part of the setup for melting and filling the fixed-point cells was a vertical furnace, Carbolite Gero HTRV 18/100/500, with a temperature range up to 1800 °C and a heating space length of 500 mm, see Figure 15. To achieve a sufficient melting of the metal materials, the temperature difference between temperature set on controller and that inside the middle of a tube in the furnace was measured with a type R thermocouple, and was found to be around 45 °C. To avoid damaging the glass or alumina tube in the furnace during this process a relatively slow increase in temperature was necessary, 300 °C per 30 min.

Figure 15: Carbolite furnace used at SMU for manufacturing fixed point cells.

SMU used 2 different types of tubes for filling the FPCs. First, a glass tube is for the Cu FP and second an alumina tube for the Fe-C, Co-C and Pd-C eutectic points. Both tubes used inner graphite parts to position the crucibles during filling as can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Left: Glass tube with graphite parts. Right: Alumina tube with graphite parts.

SMU used homemade and commercial equipment for inert atmosphere – vacuum pump and Argon gas. This inert protective atmosphere is essential to avoid burning the graphite parts and oxidizing the metals at elevated temperatures. The setup can be seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Left: Inert gas setup. Right: Close-up of the connection to the tube

For the inert atmosphere in the tube, first a vacuum was created (10 mBar), then the tube was filled with Argon gas. To ensure a constant presence of Ar gas, a constant flow of 1 l/min was maintained. A plug with 2 openings was placed in the top of the tube, the first for Argon gas flow and second for the extension stick for pushing on the piston. This setup can be seen in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Left: Connectors on top of tube. Right: Cross section of glass and alumina tube.

The filling materials had various purities and manufacturers as specified in Table 7 below:

Materials	Form	Purity	Mass	Manufacturer
Copper - Cu	1x1 mm pellets	99.99 %	300 g	American elements
Iron - Fe	powder	99.99 %	25 g	Alfa Aesar
Cobalt - Co	powder	99.995 %	250 g	ThermoFisher Scientific
Palladium - Pd	1x1 mm pellets	99.99 %	200 g	Safina
Graphite - C	powder	99.0 %	100 g	Thermo Scientific
Silver – Ag	pellets	99.999 %	100 g	Safina
Gold - Au	pellets	99.999%	100 g	Safina

Table 7 Summary of material used for the fixed-point cells at SMU.

SMU used C/C sheets from SGL Carbon with two thickness:

Folie SIGRAFLEX F08010TH (200x270x0.8) mm.

Folie SIGRAFLEX F05010TH (200x270x0.5) mm.

For each fixed-point assembly two layers of C/C sheets (thickness 0.8 mm and 0.5 mm) and two discs of C/C sheet 0.5 mm on the top (under cap) were used. The furnace was heated up at a temperature $T_{\text{melt}} + 45 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for each FP. The heating rate was around 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{h}$. The setup for preparing and filling the cells can be seen in Figure 19 below.

Figure 19: Setup for preparing and filling the FP cells with metal.

Cu

The two copper cells have been made at SMU using (1x1x1) mm pellets size shots with a purity 99.99 % from American elements in two filling steps. The cell crucible was filled with 33.0 g of Cu material and 4.8 g was the excess material left over from the piston filling method. The ingot mass was therefore 28.2 g. After filling the Cu1 FP cell, an x-ray image was taken to check the manufacturing, see Figure 20. This visual check has shown that the filling process was successful.

Figure 20: X-ray of Cu1 from two different sides.

After the melting process, a saw was used to cut off the extension from the crucible (Figure 21). This was done to separate the filling graphite elements from the fixed point itself.

Figure 21: Left: Cutting the extension with a saw to separate the cell. Right: Filled cell without end cap.

Fe-C

SMU has manufactured one Fe-C FP using 25g of powder (99.99 %) from Alfa Aesar in a two-step filling process. The cell crucible was filled with a total of 25.0 g of material with 0.9 g of excess material left in the extension from the piston filling method. The portion of C was 2% of the 25g. The filling was successful and ingot mass had the expected weight according to the literature.

Co-C

Two Cobalt-Carbon cells have been manufactured at SMU using Co powder (Figure 22) with a purity of 99.99% from Thermo Fisher Scientific in a three-step filling process. The cell crucible was filled with 32.0 g, and 5.5 g was the excess material left over in the extension from the piston filling method. The portion of C was 2% of the 32g. The filling was successful and ingot mass had the expected weight according to the literature.

Figure 22: Left: Cobalt powder. Right: Left-over Co-C from the extension.

Pd-C

One Palladium-Carbon cell (Figure 23) has been made at SMU, in one melt, using 1x1 mm pellets with a purity 99.99 % from Safina (Czech Republic company). The cell crucible was filled with 44.0 g of material (which was wrongly calculated). The portion of C was 2% of 44g (1.36 g). But the added amount of C was probably too high which could be the reason there was a large excess of material of 15.1 g in the extension. Disregarding this, the filling was successful.

Figure 23: Left: Filled Pd-C cell. Centre: X-ray of Pd-C cell. Right: Excess Pd-C material.

4.6 TUBITAK

The primary melting setup for the Copper (Cu) and iron-carbon (Fe-C) is configured for use within a Carbolite Gero three-zone resistance furnace whose upper operational temperature limit is 1200 °C. A quartz tube is placed in the furnace and sealed at back end by gas feed-through. These assemblies provide function for vacuum system for evacuation, and supply of high-purity argon for inert-atmosphere.

A set of refractory insulation bricks is positioned inside the tube to elevate the cell assembly to the isothermal zone of the furnace, typically located at the geometric centre of the three heated sections. Correct axial positioning minimises radial and axial thermal gradients at the cell. All graphite pieces, CC-sheets, and holders were baked in a vacuum at approximately 1100 °C for more than 3 h. Additionally, the parts of the crucibles were baked in an argon gas environment under similar conditions before the filling.

For cells requiring processing temperatures above 1200 °C, specifically the Co-C and Re-C eutectic fixed-points, a BB3200 furnace was employed. Both furnaces can be seen in Figure 24. In the case of the Re-C cells, the procurement of high-purity Re metal ingots was delayed. Suitable Re powder (99.999%, 5N) were finally purchased from China Rhenium Co., LTD, ZHUZHOU, CHINA, and three Re-C cells were subsequently constructed. However, these cells have not yet been characterized.

Figure 24: Left: Filling setup for temperature below 1200 °C. Right: Filling setup for temperature above 1200 °C.

Prior to loading, all ingot materials were weighed on a calibrated precision balance and homogeneously mixed to ensure compositional uniformity. For eutectic systems (Fe–C, Co–C, Re–C), calculated masses of the respective metal and graphite powder were blended to achieve the target near-eutectic composition.

Due to the lower bulk density of powder-form constituents (Co, Re, C), the filling operation for powder-based cells was executed in multiple sequential stages. Graphite Sigraflex sheets (sourced from SGL Carbon) were interleaved between the graphite sleeve and the crucible inner wall to accommodate differential thermal expansion and to ensure leak-tight sealing at operating temperature. Sheet thicknesses of 0.25 mm, 0.50 mm, or 0.75 mm were selected according to the dimensional tolerances of each cell assembly.

Table 8 provides an overview of the elemental and graphite materials employed in cell fabrication. All metallic substance were sourced at a minimum purity of 99.995 % (mass fraction) to minimise impurity-induced uncertainty.

Substance	Form	Purity
Cu	Pellet	99.999 %
Fe	Pellet	99.995 %
Co	Powder	99.995 %
Re	Powder	99.999 %
C	Powder	99.9999 %
C Sheets, Sigraflex from SGL Carbon.	Paper, 0.25 mm/0.50 mm/0.75 mm	

Table 8: Material specifications for fixed-point cell filling.

The metal-to-carbon mass ratios for the carbide eutectic cells, together with total ingot masses and residual material quantities, are summarised in Table 9.

Cell	Mass metal, g	Eutectic Composition, % mass C
Cu	31.68	-
Fe-C	27.65	4.2
Co-C	30.45	2.3
Re-C	71.85	0.9

Table 9: Metal and carbon mass ratios per cell assembly.

Cu

Three copper fixed-point cells (Figure 25) were fabricated to the TÜBİTAK-UME design specification. To maximise thermal and compositional uniformity, all three cells were filled simultaneously within the Carbolite three-zone furnace using a successive filling technique in vertical orientation. The cells were supported by an Inconel cradle and positioned at the most thermally uniform region of the heated zone, as characterised by prior thermocouple profiling. The successive filling procedure promoted homogeneous distribution of the melt and minimised void formation.

Figure 25: Copper fixed-point filling stages.

Fe-C

Two iron-carbon fixed-point cells (Figure 26) were fabricated using the Carbolite furnace under identical atmospheric and thermal conditions to the copper cells. The target composition was set close to the Fe-C eutectic (approximately 4.2 wt.% C), with the carbon mass calculated accordingly. The same successive filling methodology was applied to iron-carbon fixed-point.

Figure 26: Iron-carbon fixed-point filling stages.

Co-C

One cobalt-carbon eutectic fixed-point cell was fabricated using the BB3200 furnace. The Piston method filling technique was employed, with a total of 30.45 g metal and a carbon addition of approximately 2.3 wt.% C targeting the eutectic composition.

Re-C

Three Rhenium-carbon eutectic fixed-point cell was fabricated in the BB3200 furnace. The successive filling method was applied with a total metal charge (for 3 cells) of 215.55 g and a carbon addition of approximately 0.9 wt.% C, targeting the eutectic composition.

4.7 UL

Before the project, UL did not have any facilities for the filling of the non-contact eutectic cells. In the scope of the project a dedicated furnace for the temperatures up to the 1600 °C was designed and constructed. This furnace contains Canthal heaters, a special alumina tube, which enables an argon atmosphere and computer-controlled DC power supply, see Figure 27.

Figure 27: The custom-made filling system including furnace, power supply and argon.

All fixed-point cells were filled using a custom-built vertical filling furnace, within a sealed quartz tube with an inert argon atmosphere. A vacuum pump was used to substitute air with the inert gas. The graphite cell parts were used as delivered. Two layers of 1 mm Sigrflex graphite sheets from SGL Carbon were used for wrapping the sleeve and inside the lid. The crucibles were filled without dust hood. All non-disposable tools and containers were cleaned between uses with ethanol. All materials were kept in sealed containers before and after use.

The fixed point material used through the project was purchased from AlfaAeser, with purity of 99,9999 % (Cu, C powder, Co), 99,999 % (Fe) and from Azealis with purity 99,99% (Pd).

After successfully testing the developed furnace, it was used for filling the cells. In total 1 Cu cells, 1 Co-C, 1 Fe-C and 1 Pd cells were made. The details of the cells can be found in Table 10 below:

Fixed point	Name	Number of filling steps	Amount of metal material [g]	Amount of carbon material [g]	FP mass [g]
Cu	Cu1	2	32	-	54
Fe-C	Fe-C1	2	25	0,89	52
Co-C	Co-C1	2	32	0,65	53
Pd-C	Pd-C1	2	45	1,35	55

Table 10: Summary of cells filled at UL.

Cu

One copper cell has been manufactured at UL using high purity powder. The fixed-point cell was filled with all the metal in one melt and there were no noticeable problems.

Fe-C

One iron-carbon fixed-point has been manufactured using a mixture of iron powder, with high purity and graphite powder. The fixed-point cell was filled with all the metal-carbon mixture in one melt and there were no noticeable problems.

Co-C

One cobalt-carbon fixed-point cell has been manufactured using a mixture of cobalt powder of high purity from Alpha Aesar and graphite powder. The fixed-point cell was filled with all the metal-carbon mixture in one melt and there were no noticeable problems.

Pd-C

One palladium-carbon fixed-point cell has been manufactured using palladium powder with a purity of 99.99% (4n) from Azelis and graphite powder.

5 Fixed-point cell characterisation and optimisation

The sections below describe the testing, characterisation and optimisation of the fixed-point cells at the different NMLs as part of the work in the MultiFixRad project.

5.1 CMI

Due to technical issue with the Thermogauge furnace (water leak in the circuit and the need to replace several parts of the furnace) which was originally meant to be used for the HTFPs cells realisation, only the Co-C cell was realised.

Co-C

The cell was placed in a three-zone furnace, with very uniform central zone (

Figure 28). The cell is placed in a central region, which means homogeneity of the temperature distribution alongside the cell is better than 0,5 °C.

Figure 28: Homogeneity of the CMI three zone furnace, where the constructed Co-C cell was realised.

To realise the fixed point, it was necessary to place cell into a cell holder, in order to fit the cell in the centre of a tube with diameter of 29 mm in diameter (Figure 29). Some additional graphite and insulation parts are

placed around the cell to protect it (Figure 30). Argon flow was brought to the furnace from both sides. A sufficient flow was determined to be at a level of 1.5 l/min from both sides.

Figure 29: Co-C cell fitted in a cell holder.

Figure 30: Final setup of the components placed in the 3-zone furnace for Co-C measurement.

In total, 4 measurement cycles were realised. The first two were compromised due to the insulation in front of the fixed-point, when the walls of the insulation were in the field of view of the pyrometer, resulting in a low temperature. The number of graphite and insulation parts were therefore adjusted.

For the measurement of the cell a linear pyrometer LP5 ($\lambda = 650 \text{ nm}$) was used, with a diameter of the measurement spot about 1 mm.

For testing the cell, the furnace was programmed to run the temperature cycles automatically, with one measurement run containing 4 melting/freezing cycles before the whole system cooled down. The results from run 3 and 4 is shown in Figure 31. The pyrometer was visually focused on the opening of the fixed-point cavity at ambient temperature.

Figure 31: Records of the third and fourth measurement cycles of the Co-C cell at CMI.

As a temperature of the fixed- point realisation was evaluated, the point of inflection and quality of the cell was assessed based on the melting range of the plateaus. The inflection point is found through a 3rd order polynomial fit of the melting curve. Liquidus and solidifying points are also determined to evaluate the melting range of the prepared cell. The tangent method is used to determine these points. The melting range of the prepared cell was identified as approximately 150 mK.

5.2 DFM/DTU

The partners DFM and DTU collaborated on the creation and realization of fixpoints. In the following the work will be described in common.

Furnace

A horizontal 3 zone oven was fabricated for the purpose of realization of the ITS-90 at DFM and DTU. It was created using high temperature insulation material, MoS₂ heating elements capable of achieving 1800 °C arranged in an optimized 3 zone configuration, and an alumina tube in the centre.

Figure 32: Construction of DFM/DTU horizontal oven using MoS₂ heating elements.

The homogeneity of the oven was confirmed using a type S thermocouple mounted at different depth using a configuration similar to the one used for fixpoint realisation. A gradient of much less than a degree was established. The construction of the oven is shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33.

A custom aluminium end stop was fabricated to facilitate argon flow from the back of the oven. It was led through several graphite sheet rings of 5 mm thickness in a ceramic tube. The fixpoint was mounted in a graphite holder made to centre the fixpoint in the alumina tube and homogenize the temperature of the fixpoint.

In front of the fixpoint was a custom cut graphite insulation piece and in front of this a ring of the 5 mm thickness graphite sheet. A high temperature insulation funnel was placed in front of this, enabling good visibility of the fixpoint aperture in the centre of the oven.

Figure 33: DFM/DTU horizontal MoS₂ oven demonstration. The imaging pyrometer is measuring a fixpoint realisation.

Radiation thermometer

An imaging pyrometer was designed and implemented for high performance relative radiative pyrometry. The optical setup is following the layout of the LP5 but implemented with a temperature stabilized camera as the detector. It was proven before MultiFixRad that this is a feasible approach and enables direct imaging of the fixpoint. This is very useful for alignment as a viewfinder, as well as for measuring homogeneity in a systematised manner. Additionally, the imaging approach enables a variable size of source which has proven interesting for the fixpoint with different apertures. The pyrometer is shown measuring the RISE blackbody oven in Figure 34.

Figure 34: DFM Pyrometer measuring blackbody at RISE.

The size of source of the pyrometer was measured using the direct method. The compromise of spot size and SSE is a problem with the Thorlabs 75 mm lens, and the measurements presented at the time of writing was limited by an SSE of 0.997 at $\text{Ø}3\text{mm}$. A conservative choice of uncertainty of this 0.997 was included in the uncertainty budgets for the measurements, and a plan for implementing a higher quality lens is under way.

Realisations

The construction of the 3-zone horizontal oven took longer than planned and only the Co-C and Pd-C fixpoints were realized. These joined the already established copper and silver fixpoints of DFM. The Co-C fixpoint was realized 3 times confirming performance of the setup. The Pd-C was realized 8 times over 4 days. The realizations were performed by ramping to 10 K above the melting plateau and freezing by ramping to 10 K below the melting plateau. An example of the imaging that the imaging pyrometer enables is shown in Figure 35, where the colder temperature of the centre of the fixpoint cavity is obvious compared to the brighter and warmer temperature of the rest of the cell and oven.

Figure 35: Example of imaging of a melting fixpoint. The dark center is the cavity of the fixpoint cell showing darker and thus colder temperature than the surrounding material..

5.3 JV

Furnace

The furnace used for cell realisation at JV is a Carbolite-Gero TF1-16-18 furnace. It is a single-zone tube furnace with interchangeable work tubes. JV currently has one work tube with inner diameter 25 mm and another with inner diameter 50 mm. During operation with a fixed point, the back opening is sealed and a feed-through for Ar gas is installed. The front opening remains open at all times, but Ar is injected into the work tube using a thin steel pipe that extends a few cm into the furnace (see Figure 36 below). Disks from graphite wool is inserted into the work tube from both sides to improve the thermal gradients. The disks in the back have a $\text{\O}5$ mm centred hole, while the disks in front have gradually larger holes to ensure an unobstructed light path from the blackbody opening to the radiometer objective lens (see sketch in Figure 37 below). A small improvement of the setup was used in the final realisations of the Ag, Fe-C and Pd-C points. Here the work tube diameter was increased to 50 mm, and the fixed-point cell was placed in a graphite holder. The graphite holder improves the thermal homogeneity slightly and protects the cell better. The holder is similar to that used by RISE.

Figure 36: Images showing the back (left) and front (right) of the furnace used to realise the plateaux. The back of the work tube is sealed except for a feedthrough for Argon gas flow. In the front the Argon gas is injected a short distance into the work tube, which is otherwise exposed to ambient air.

Figure 37: A sketch of the work tube with the fixed-point cell and insulation rings installed. The cell is located slightly toward the back, since the heat loss at the front leads to a slightly oblique temperature profile inside the work tube.

Furnace characteristics

The furnace controller regulates the temperature based on feedback thermocouples located outside the work tube, in the heated volume of the furnace. The control parameters are not optimised for a specific application. Typical overshoot when reaching a new setpoint is around 3 °C, which is similar at all temperatures above around 1000 °C. A similar undershoot is seen when the controller reaches a lower setpoint.

Figure 38: Temperature profile near the centre of the work tube, inside the graphite holder for fixed point cells. The left panel shows a profile obtained with a thermocouple at approximately 1000 °C, in the Ø25 mm work tube and without any additional insulation. The right panel shows a profile obtained with the radiation thermometer aiming at the back of an empty fixed-point crucible, using the Ø50 mm work tube, the graphite holder in place, insulation in the back, and a constant flow of Argon gas.

The furnace gradients have been measured axially in two ways, with the corresponding profiles shown in Figure 38. The two cases were recorded at approximately 1000 °C and 1300 °C, respectively. In the first case the Ø25 mm work tube was installed, with no additional insulation in either end. A thermocouple was installed on a translation stage which was programmed to cycle through a set of positions spaced 10 mm apart. For each position the thermocouple was held for approximately 15 minutes to allow sufficient time for stabilisation. Within the central 4 cm, corresponding to roughly the length of the fixed-point cells, the temperature span is approximately 1.5 °C. This span should be a worst case at that temperature for two reasons. During experiments additional insulation is added inside the work tube to improve stability, and the metal ingot in the cell is surrounded by various layers of graphite which conducts heat well axially and should reduce the gradient slightly.

In the second case the Ø50 mm work tube was used, with an empty fixed-point crucible mounted inside the graphite holder. The crucible was turned such that the back pointed towards the radiation thermometer and used as the target object. The holder was placed inside the work tube with the front face approximately 8 cm from the centre of the furnace, and hence the crucible back wall was located one cm closer to the centre. Insulation was added to the back, and Argon gas was supplied at a constant rate throughout the experiment. Once the furnace temperature had stabilised, an alumina rod was used to push the graphite holder away from the opening of the work tube to cover a range of positions until the peak temperature was recorded. The radiation thermometer was aligned and pointed towards the target. After each change in position, the target assembly was allowed to settle after the cold shock from the rod. The detector voltage was converted to temperature using our own calibration at fixed points. The temperature span is similar to the first case, around 1.5 °C over the crucible length.

Radiation thermometer

The radiometer used is a custom-made device assembled from commercial optical, mechanical and electrical component. The optics and opto-mechanics are mostly from Thorlabs, except the detector which is a Hamamatsu detector package with integrated preamplifier. Several iterations of the radiometer have been used to measure the plateaus, which may affect some of the features seen in the data. It is not described in detail here.

Inert atmosphere and work tube fragility

Ensuring an inert atmosphere in the furnace, while also maintaining free line of sight, has been one of the major practical challenges in the project. A balance must be found between a sufficient Argon flow to avoid oxidation of the fixed-point crucible, and too high Ar flow. The latter has an obvious disadvantage in Ar

consumption but also may lead to larger than necessary cooling of the crucible. During the project, JV has mostly used a high-pressure Ar flask and a manual control valve to control the flow. The typical duration of an experiment, including heating and cooling from/to room temperature, is 10-15 hours. Without any automation in the Ar flow control the flow was typically opened at room temperature, and without a measured flow rate the operator would rather err on the high side to protect the crucibles. However, when the Ø50 mm work tube was used Ar flow was also increased to compensate for the increased loss through the furnace opening and the larger heated volume.

In one of the experiments at the Pd-C point the graphite insulation pads inserted in front of the crucibles started to disintegrate at high temperature. This caused concern that perhaps the graphite holder or the crucible itself was in danger of oxidative damage, and the Ar flow was increased. In response to this increased flow the entire assembly was pushed forward by the increased pressure at the back and struck the small steel Ar pipe (see Figure 36, right) immersed in the work tube. The experiment was abandoned, and when the furnace had cooled it was clear that the work tube had fractured (see Figure 39).

Figure 39: Fractured work tube after sudden increase in Argon flow at high temperature.

A plausible explanation is that the sudden change in temperature gradients. When the Ar flow was increased this probably started to cool the work tube. When the entire hot graphite holder a few seconds later suddenly moved forward to the cooler part of the work tube, it was exposed to a sudden increase in temperature locally, causing high thermal stress and eventual fracture. If this is correct, a more careful operation of the Ar flow is needed in the future, and JV is currently upgrading the laboratory for this purpose.

Plateaux realisations at JV

The overview in Table 11 summarises the work at JV.

Fixed point	Repeated realisations	Useable plateaus
Ag	6	4
Cu	5	5
Fe-C	10	10
Co-C	6	3
Pd-C	16	6

Table 11: Overview of realisations at JV.

The Ag, Fe-C and Pd-C have been realised using both work tubes.

At the highest temperature, the Pd-C point, the inert gas atmosphere is more challenging to maintain in the furnace. Figure 40 shows two example photos of the Pd-C cell after prolonged exposure to the furnace environment at its transition point. Some discoloration is clearly visible, and a hint of deformation can be identified at the front face if a finger is used to gently touch the surface.

Figure 40: Images showing the discoloration of the Pd-C cell after operation. The cell does not have any obvious weak spots, although there is a slight deformation towards the edges on the front face, as evidenced by gently feeling the surface with a fingertip.

Pd-C

Figure 41: Four example plateaus at the Pd-C point, shown in signal voltage but with corresponding temperatures shown on the right axis. The temperature conversion is based on the two-point scheme using an average signal obtained at the Cu and Pd-C points using the $\varnothing 25$ mm work tube. The first three examples include the freeze. In the fourth case the freeze could not be measured because the line of sight was partially blocked by the insulation disks collapsing due to oxidation caused by insufficient Ar flow. In the other cases the difference between melt and freeze is approximately 0.2 K, if the freeze is taken as the peak of the process just behind the recalcination dip.

Figure 41 shows four example plateaus for the Pd-C cell. Example 1 was recorded in the $\varnothing 50$ mm work tube with the additional graphite holder. The furnace setpoint is around 5 °C above the melting temperature, resulting in a long and flat plateau. The other three examples were recorded in the $\varnothing 25$ mm work tube with a higher setpoint (compared with the melting temperature). The effect on the plateau duration is clearly seen in

the graphs, although for the first example the graphite holder is also acting as a buffer to the furnace overshoot and further helps to extend the transition process.

The freeze plateaus are short and with a distinct linear downward trend. However, the peak freeze and the POI are quite close in all three shown examples, corresponding to less than 0.2 K. The scatter between the POIs is larger, amounting to around 0.8 K in the examples shown. Most of the difference may be explained by a modification in the radiation thermometer, where the filter has been heated from a little less than 22 °C in examples 2-4 to around 28 °C in example 1. However, there are other effects at play, too: (i) the size-of-source effect (SSE), (ii) the alignment of the radiometer, and (iii) the furnace conditions.

For the SSE, the background temperature around the cavity opening will generate an additional signal, which are partly transmitted through the optics and detected by the photodetector. When the over-temperature is increased, the magnitude of the SSE signal also increases, and this leads to an apparent (but not real) increase in POI. The alignment of the radiation thermometer is difficult, because there is a lack of contrast in the image generated in the viewfinder camera when the temperature is high. The Pd-C point is particularly difficult in the current setup. The result of poor alignment is similar to the SSE, by admitting a contribution of light generated by the temperature of the front face of the fixed-point cell rather than the blackbody itself. The furnace conditions, primarily the temperature gradients, will affect how the melting process proceeds, and may result in unwanted temperature gradients inside cavity. This effect may also lead to the trend seen especially in example 3 where there is a distinct transition about halfway through the melt to a faster increase in radiation signal than in the initial phase. This could happen if a bridge of molten ingot reaches the inner wall of the blackbody, exposing that surface section to the furnace temperature instead of retaining the melting temperature. This affects the attribution of a POI in two ways: firstly, by corrupting the main signal with a slightly larger contribution from a hotter background, and secondly by affecting the POI identification algorithm which would tend to select a point near the (arbitrary) point where the apparent temperature increase becomes faster.

Co-C

Figure 42: Example plateau for the Co-C cell. The left axis shows the measured signal voltage. The right axis shows the corresponding temperature if a calibration curve is generated based on the manufacturer’s specification of the transmission properties of the interference filter used, and on the measured signals at the Cu and Pd-C points (i.e. the two-point scheme).

The Co-C cell was tested repeatedly without success. A typical “best case” plateau is shown in Figure 42. There are three features to note from the example.

Firstly, the attributed transition temperature is around 4 °C lower than the expected temperature of 1324.24 °C. The temperature attribution is based on the Cu and Pd-C fixed points of Justervesenet: in principle, the

difference could be due to bad Cu and Pd-C cells. However, Justervesenets pyrometer has also been used to measure the plateau of the Pd-C cell of RISE using their furnace setup, yielding a difference of less than 30 mK. The plateaus for both the Cu and Pd-C cells at Justervesenet also appear to be of much higher quality just from a qualitative, visual assessment of the plateaus. Secondly, the melting plateau is never flat. While part of this steep signal increase could be attributed to e.g. misalignment, this seems to be a robust feature of Justervesenets cell and is seen across multiple attempts to realise the melt. And finally, if a POI attribution was attempted the most reasonable value is represented by the upper black line in the figure; the lower black line is a reasonable value for the freeze. The difference amounts to around 1.5 K, which is a large value.

Impurities in the Co metal is the main hypothesis to explain the observed Co-C behaviour. The metal used has not been subject to independent chemical analysis. The supplier information claims purity better than 4N. If this is the case it may be difficult to explain the large discrepancy in the melting temperature. The effect of impurities depends on the species. While most elements will lower the melting temperature compared to the pure limit, this is not the case for some metallic elements. Furthermore, even if all impurities contribute to lowering the melting point, the impurity concentration must be quite high to explain 4 K. However, alternative explanations do not seem more compelling. Furnace conditions might contribute to an irregular melt inside the ingot, but the furnace conditions for the Co-C cell are similar or better than for the Pd-C cell: the furnace gradients near the cell are similar, and the radiative heat loss through the open front should be significantly larger for the Pd-C case. Various geometric effects could also be considered, such as the SSE of the radiation thermometer or the effective emissivity of the cavity, but they ought to be quite similar to that of the other cells, and worse at higher temperature.

Example plateau analysis

Figure 43: Example plateau at the Pd-C point. The plateau is considered a good plateau. The blue line is the measurements. The red points are, from left to right, the initiation of the melt as identified by the inflection point of the blue line, the POI of the plateau, and the end of the melt identified as the inflection point on the blue line. The red dashed lines are the tangent lines in each of the red points. The black point is one possible determination of the liquidus point.

Justervesenet currently uses the point-of-inflection to identify the melting temperature. The plateaus are analysed in a semi-manual way; by identifying the time window manually from the time the furnace is heated through to the stage where the melting process ends, and the temperature corresponds to the furnace temperature again. Smaller sub-windows are then first identified at the start of the melting curve, and the point-of-inflection of the signal is used as the point of first melt. The final melt is similarly identified at the end of the plateau (first and last red dots in Figure 43, respectively). The point-of-inflection of the melt is identified by fitting a 3rd order polynomial to the central, flat part, and computing the POI from the polynomial equation. The uncertainty (type A) of this determination is taken as the fit uncertainty of the polynomial at the POI.

Currently, an estimate for the liquidus point is taken as the somewhat arbitrary crossing point between the POI tangents at the melting point and the end of melt (shown as the black point in the figure). Justervesenet will implement widely accepted methods instead at a later point (after the project ends). The code is implemented in Matlab and will be published soon after the end of the project.

5.4 RISE

All fixed-points were realised in two furnaces, one Entech ETF 50/18-III 3-zone furnace and one Thermo Gauge with one heating zone. The maximum working temperature in the Entech furnace is 1750 °C, so for temperatures above this the Thermo Gauge furnace was used.

Entech furnace

The Entech ETF 50/18-III furnace has a 50 mm ceramic tube which is heated by heating elements, placed next to the tube, that can be controlled in three zones. To be able to use this furnace for the 25 mm diameter fixed-points, a two-part graphite holder was manufactured, which can be seen in Figure 44 below.

Figure 44: Graphite holder for fitting the fixed-point cells in the Entech furnace.

In addition to the holder, two cylindrical graphite blocks were placed in front of the holder, and two in the back. The cylinders had channels along the sides, and a hole in the middle for shielding gas and for the pyrometer to be able to measure the temperature in the cell. Several 10 mm thick felt disks were also placed in front and back of the cylinders. This was all done to improve the homogeneity of the temperature in the furnace, as well as providing sacrificial material in case the supply of shielding gas is not perfect.

Thermo Gauge furnace

The Thermo Gauge furnace is a one zone furnace where the heat is generated by running a high current through a 1" (inner diameter) graphite tube in which the fixed-point cell is placed. Several disks of 10 mm graphite felt were placed in front and back of the cell as insulation in an attempt to decrease the temperature gradients around the cell. The felt disks in front of the cell had decreasingly smaller hole in the centre the closer they were to fixed-point for the pyrometer. Care was taken to ensure that no part of the felt was in the field of view of the pyrometer. The disks in the back also had a central hole for the pyrometer connected to the temperature regulator to be able to measure the temperature of the bottom of the fixed-point cell.

Ag

The silver fixed-point cell was placed in the holder pictured above, which in turn was positioned in the tube in the Entech furnace so that the centre of the cell was in the centre of the tube.

The furnace was first ramped to about 10 K below the melting temperature, where it was left to stabilise. It was then ramped to 10 K above the melting temperature with 2 K/min. After the super cool, the furnace was set to 3 K below melt. Both the melt and freeze plateau were as expected, and the freeze lasted about one hour. During the whole procedure the zone behind the cell was set to 5 K above the middle zone, and the zone in the front to 6 K above.

Argon was used as a shielding gas and was fed into the tube from the front and back with a flow of about 3 l/min. In the back through the cap covering the opening, and in the front through a small tube ending about 100 mm into the larger tube.

The fixed-point has been realised three times using the same settings and producing similar results. No further optimisation has been made.

Cu

The copper fixed-point cell has been realised multiple times, at least 15, in the Entech furnace. It was placed in the holder pictured above, which in turn was positioned in the tube in the furnace so that the centre of the cell was in the centre of the tube.

The furnace was first ramped to about 10 K below the melting temperature, where it was left to stabilise. It was then ramped to 10 K above the melting temperature with 1 K/min and left there for 30 min before ramping to 4 K below melt with 1 K/min. After the super cool, the furnace was set to 3 K below melt. Both the melt and freeze plateau were as expected and the freeze lasted more than one hour. During the whole procedure the zone behind and in front of the cell was set to 5 K above the middle zone.

For the other realisations settings have been similar, with some using up to 3 K/min ramps and slightly different set points and dwell times. All freezing plateaus have had temperatures with similar values, and the duration of the plateau have been dependent on the set point, as expected.

The copper cell was also realised two times in the Thermo Gauge furnace to test if this furnace would give compatible results. Due to not being familiar with the controller for the furnace the settings were not optimised but the goal was to keep them close to that of the other furnace to be able to compare the results. The temperature of the freezing plateau was in the same range as in the other furnace.

Fe-C

The iron-carbon eutectic fixed-point has been realised two times in the Entech furnace and four times in the Thermo Gauge furnace, with two melts each time during three occasions. In the Entech furnace it was placed in the centre inside the holder, with graphite blocks and felt in front and back, as described above. In the Thermo Gauge furnace it was placed in the centre of the tube with one disk of graphite felt insulation behind and two in front of the cell. The set points used for the realization in the Entech furnace, and the second one in the Thermo Gauge was 15 °C below and above the melting temperature. For the other one it was 10 °C. The ramp was set to 2 °C/min for all of them.

The melting plateau was similar for the two melts with a setpoint 15 °C over, but significantly shorter for the other one. Both the melting and freezing plateaus were better in the Entech furnace, likely because of smaller temperature gradients. All melting plateaus were usable and gave reasonable values.

Co-C

The cobalt-carbon fixed point has been realised nine times in the Entech furnace and three times in the Thermo Gauge furnace. In the Entech furnace it was placed in the centre inside the holder, with graphite blocks and felt in front and back, as described above. In the Thermo Gauge furnace it was placed in the centre of the tube with one disk of graphite felt insulation behind and several in front of the cell. The set points used were about

15 °C over the melting temperature with a ramp of 2 °C/min in the Entech, and 20 °C/min in the Thermo Gauge furnace. This cell was used to study the effect of placing the fixed point off-centre in the furnace. The effect on the melting temperature from moving the cell ± 20 mm in the furnace was determined to be small.

Pd-C

The palladium-carbon fixed point has been realised nine times in the Entech and Thermo Gauge furnaces. It was placed in the centre of the tube with one disk of graphite felt insulation behind and several in front of the cell. The set points used were about 15 to 25 °C over the melting temperature, with a ramp of between 2 and 20 °C/min. This was done in order to observe any possible effect of the ramp and set point on the melting temperature. It was determined that the settings on the furnace did not significantly change the melting temperature, although it did affect the length and shape of the plateau. After these tests it was noticed that there was a small amount of metal in the opening of the cavity and, after disassembly, that the sleeve was cracked.

Re-C

The rhenium-carbon fixed point has been realised at least fourteen times in the Thermo Gauge furnace. It was placed in the centre of the tube with one disk of graphite felt insulation behind and several in front of the cell. The set points used were about 15 to 25 °C over the melting temperature, with a ramp between 2 and 20 °C/min. The plateau of this fixed point was not very well defined, and the calculated melting temperature was several K under that published. The variation in set point and ramp speed was to try to find settings that resulted in a better-defined plateau. Moving the cell in the furnace was also tested, to determine if the problem was due to temperature gradients but did not give any better result. It was finally determined that the pore plateau was likely due to impurities in the rhenium metal. During testing it was noted that the super-cooling of this fixed point was sometimes very large, exceeding 100 K.

5.5 SMU

SMU used two furnaces for measuring the melting and freezing plateaus of the eutectic fixed-point cells. Specific details of the used furnaces are as in Table 12 below.

Furnace	Isotech Oberon	Vecstar
Temperature range	Up to 1090 °C	Up to 1550 °C
FP	Cu	Fe-C, Co-C and Pd-C
Heating zones	One / Sodium heatpipe	One zone
Vacuuming (before)	No	Yes

Table 12: Summary of furnaces at SMU.

The fixed points were tested in these 2 furnaces with a Chino IR-RST65H pyrometer. Spot size was around 1 mm at a distance of 800mm. Temperature range from 1000 °C to 3000 °C in 3-step selection. Spectral responsivity is 650 nm. Output from pyrometer is 0 V to 10 V DC measured using a 2-channel multimeter, Keysight 34420A with a sample rate of 3 seconds.

Isotech Oberon

For the Cu fixed point cell, a commercial sodium heat-pipe furnace by Isotech was used together with partly custom graphite parts. The heating time with this setup is about 4 hours, with a flow of inert gas (Argon) of around 1l/min.

Figure 45: Isotech Oberon furnace.

Vecstar Furnace for high temperature

For the Fe-C, Co-C and Pd-C fixed point cell a Vecstar Furnace was used with a temperature range from 600 °C to 1550 °C. The furnace is open from both sides with a 60 mm diameter alumina tube inside. There is one heating zone in the furnace, heating an area of 450 mm in the middle of the tube. The furnace and its components can be seen in Figure 46 Figure 48.

The tube is closed off by high temperature resistant mineral wool on one side. The fixed-point is positioned surrounded by in-house manufactured graphite parts. In front of the fixed point are O-rings with different diameter. Inert gas is supplied via an alumina tube from the open side. Before setting the desired furnace temperature the tube was evacuated to create a vacuum and then filled by inert gas (Argon). Between 1 to 2 l/min flow was used to maintain the inert atmosphere.

Figure 46: Vecstar Furnace.

Figure 47: Schematic overview of the furnace.

Figure 48: Graphite O-rings in front of the cell.

Realizations

Table 13 below summarises the number of realisations for each fixed-point cell and the of repeatability.

Cell	Number of realizations	Repeatability / °C (after drift correction)
Ag1		~ 0,1
Au1	2	~ 0,1
Cu1	8	~ 0,1
Cu2	10	~ 0,1
Fe-C1	10	~ 0,2
Co-C1	7	~ 0,4
Co-C2	11	~ 0,4
Pd-C1	10	~ 0,3
Pd-C2	9	~ 0,1

Table 13: Summary of realisations.

Ag

The silver fixed point was manufactured in one step using 40 g of silver. The cell was realised in the Isotech Oberon furnace with set points +6 °C / - 3 °C over/under the melting temperature. The resulting freezing plateaus can be seen in Figure 49 below.

Figure 49: Fixed point Ag1 realisation in Isotech Oberon.

Au

The gold fixed point cell was made using 70 g of gold pellets in two steps. The set points for the furnace were +7 °C / -2 °C and gave the following plateaus (Figure 50).

Figure 50: The melting and freezing plateau for Au1 gold cell.

Cu

In the Isotech Oberon furnace there are not many options for positioning the fixed-point in the inside of tube. The optimization of the realization of the fixed-point could therefore only be done by changing the furnace set points and finding the optimal plateau (Figure 51). After multiple settings were tried out the best option for plateau slope, duration and difference between melting and freezing temperatures were (+4°C to + 6°C) and (-6°C to -8°C).

Based on the results it was determined that the copper fixed-point works well and the setup for realisation is also adequate.

Figure 51: Cu2 copper fixed-point realisation during 3 days, with different set points.

Fe-C

For this fixed-point the Vecstar furnace was used. Based on the measurements from other fixed points it was decided to place the fixed-point in the middle of the furnace using six graphite O-rings. The value of the point of inflection (POI) was almost the same (in the range of 0,2 °C) using different set points below and above the melting temperature, see Figure 52. The POI for the first realisation was usually higher than the following. The POI for the eutectic fixed-points were estimated by the first derivate of the melting plateau.

Figure 52: The slope and diff POI base on diff set +/- temperature to Fe-C1.

Co-C

Despite using the same procedure to make this fixed-point as for the other FPs (Fe-C, Pd-C), the final ingot weight being almost the same as describe in literature, and using 99,99% pure cobalt metal, the results were not good. Different positions, number of O-rings etc. were used, but the results were the same, as seen in Figure 53 below.

Figure 53: Co-C realisations showing a badly defined melting plateau.

The main problem is that the plateau is not useable, the slope is too steep. It is therefore hard to find the POI and when it was calculated, the POI temperature was almost 4 °C below the nominal value. The reason is probably the purity of the cobalt metal.

Pd-C

The highest temperature fixed-point that SMU has manufactured was the Pd-C. Despite some issues during the manufacturing process, this FP seems to be working correctly according to measured data. Again, multiple different temperature setups above and below the POI were tested to achieve the optimal realization. Also, different positions in the furnace and number of O-ring setups were tried as well. The results were almost the same, but the best was when the fixed-point was in the middle of the furnace and six O-rings were used as insulators, see Figure 54.

Figure 54: The plateaux realisations for different set points and positions in the furnace for Pd-C1.

5.6 TUBITAK

TÜBİTAK-UME used the HTBB 3500M high-temperature for measuring the melting and freezing plateaus of the fixed-point cells, as shown in Figure 55 below.

Figure 55: HTBB 3500M high-temperature furnace.

The radiometer used in this study is an LP5 linear pyrometer operating as a radiation thermometer with a central wavelength of 650 nm. LP5 has a spot size of 0.7 mm at an 800 mm focal plane. The instrument was mounted on a three-axis precision translation stage assembly and two independent tilt-adjustment mechanisms to enable reproducible optical alignment with the cavity aperture of the fixed-point cell, minimizing off-axis vignetting and ensuring representative cavity radiance sampling.

Realizations

Table 14 below summarises the total number of realisations performed for each fixed-point cell, along with the operational status determined following the measurement campaign.

Cell	Number of realizations	Status
Cu-01	15	Operational
Cu-02	15	Failed
Cu-03	4	Operational
Fe-C1	15	Operational
Fe-C2	0	Failed
Co-C1	5	Operational

Table 14: Realisations at TUBITAK.

Cu

Following the filling procedure, each copper fixed-point cell was individually characterized in the HTBB 3500M furnace using the LP5 radiation thermometer. All realisations were conducted using furnace setpoints of +15°C above and -15°C below the copper freezing point (1084.62°C on ITS-90) to establish well-defined melting and freezing plateaus. Cu-01 and Cu-03 exhibited comparable thermal behaviour, with repeatability within 10 mK across all realizations. Cu-02, however, produced systematically lower radiance temperature readings relative to the other two cells throughout its realization sequence, see Figure 56. Post-measurement inspection revealed mechanical failure at the base of the Cu-02 cell, which is consistent with the observed radiance deficit and plateau instability, and the cell was subsequently removed from the measurement campaign.

Figure 56: Comparison of the filled Cu cells. (red dots plot – a broken cell).

Fe-C

Based on optical geometry data established during the Real-K project, the Fe-C fixed-point cell was positioned before the 11th graphite ring of the furnace element to achieve optimized thermal uniformity across the cell cavity. The furnace setpoints were set to +15°C and -15°C relative to the iron-carbon eutectic fixed-point temperature for all realizations. Fe-C1 demonstrated stable and reproducible plateau behaviour throughout the measurement campaign, see Figure 57. Plateau repeatability was evaluated using the MultiFixRadSoft software and determined to be within 20 mK. The Fe-C2 cell, however, could not be realized due to cracks formed in the side wall. Together with the short melting duration, this also triggered a malfunction of the PID controller, resulting in an irreversible mechanical failure of the cell prior to any realization attempt.

Figure 57: Fe-C1 cell realization.

Co-C

The cobalt-carbon (Co-C) eutectic fixed-point cell was successfully realized for the first time during this campaign, see Figure 58. The point-of-inflection (POI) repeatability was determined to be within 20 mK, which is satisfactory for an initial realization of this fixed point. However, a systematic ramp was observed across the melting plateau, attributable to a sub-optimal axial positioning of the cell within the furnace bore, resulting in an asymmetric thermal gradient across the graphite cavity. This effect is consistent with known sensitivity of eutectic plateaus to furnace uniformity. Therefore, during the investigations, the Co-C cells were positioned at the centre of the furnace tube, behind an additional diaphragm introduced to improve the temperature uniformity in the central region of the furnace. This configuration was similar to that employed for the HTFPs within the EU EMPIR project “Real-K”.

Figure 58: Co-C1 cell realization.

5.7 UL

All fixed points were realised in the custom horizontal furnace, built at UL. The furnace tube is 25 mm in diameter and 70 cm long, with 7 heating zones evenly spaced along the central 30 cm of the furnace.

Temperature gradients were measured by 13 thermocouples, located within the ceramic tube assembly and spaced to correspond to heating zones and their midpoints. Temperature is regulated with a LabView environment on a dedicated computer, providing control of temperature zones, as well as heating slopes and thermal gradient along the depth of the tube. Controlled gradients were tested however a setting of zero gradient was found as optimal for plateau realisation.

Argon of 5n purity is supplied through the sealed rear end of the ceramic tube. The fixed-point cell was inserted in the centre of the furnace. Sacrificial graphite and ceramic tubes were placed in front of the cell to limit convective currents and consume intruding oxygen. The setup for realising the fixed-point cells can be seen in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Measuring set up in the laboratory.

The pyrometer was positioned and centred using a coordinate table with two rotational axes. A melting or freezing plateau was induced during a scan of the cell front surface to increase contrast of the cavity, and a bell-like radial sigmoid curve was fitted to obtain the centre of the cavity, as in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Pyrometer scan of the cavity of the fixed-point cell and centre fitting using radial sigmoid geometry.

Cu

The copper fixed-point has been realised 9 times before and 11 times after optimisation. Freezing plateaus were induced with furnace temperature ramping with -1 K/min from 10 K above to 10 K below the freezing temperature of copper. The point of inflection was characterized at the point of first derivative crossing 0 in negative direction. For optimal characterisation, the noise in pyrometer measurements and the first derivative were mitigated using 20 second moving average filter. The standard deviation of inflection points of repeated plateaus with optimised settings was 4.5 mK.

Fe-C

The iron-carbon eutectic fixed-point has been realised 44 times after optimisation. Melting plateaus were induced with furnace temperature ramping by 2 K/min up to 10 K above the freezing temperature of copper. The point of inflection was characterized at the time of second derivative crossing 0 in positive direction. The noise in pyrometer measurements and the first derivative was mitigated using 2 and 4 minute moving average filters, whereas for the second derivative, the averaging window width was set individually to one quarter of the plateau duration. The standard deviation of inflection points of repeated plateaus with optimised settings was 13 mK.

Co-C

The cobalt-carbon eutectic fixed-point has been realised 18 times after optimisation. Melting plateaus were induced with furnace temperature ramping by 2 K/min up to 10 K above the freezing temperature of copper, however results with ± 15 K seem to be more repeatable at slightly higher inflection temperature. The noise in pyrometer measurements and the first derivative was reduced by using 4- and 8-minute moving average filters, whereas for the second derivative, the averaging window width was set individually to one quarter of the plateau duration. The standard deviation of inflection points of repeated plateaus with optimised settings was 60 mK.

Pd-C

The palladium-carbon eutectic fixed-point has been realised 16 times after optimisation. Melting plateaus were induced with furnace temperature ramping by 0.5 K/min up to 5 K above the freezing temperature of copper. The noise in pyrometer measurements and the first derivative were mitigated using 2 and 4 minute moving average filters, whereas for the second derivative, the averaging window width was set individually to one quarter of the plateau duration. The palladium-carbon cell was damaged in measurements due to oxygen

intrusion in the furnace, resulting in decreasing inflection temperature measurements over time, see Figure 61. The standard deviation of inflection points of repeated plateaus was 591 mK.

Figure 61: Palladium-carbon cell inflection points and plateau ranges over repeated realisations.

6 Conclusions

This report summarises the work done by several NMI/DIs (JV, RISE, CMI, SMU, UL, LNE-CNAM, TUBITAK and DFM/DTU) in filling, testing, optimising and realising a range of different metal/metal-carbon high temperature fixed point cells in the project MultiFixRad. The fixed points in question have been Al, Ag, Au, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C, Pt-C and Re-C, with a total of about 40 being produced during the project.

The fixed point cells were of a hybrid design based on cells developed, and previously used, at LNE-CNAM. They were ordered in bulk for all partners in the project and were manufactured using graphite of high purity and density. The metals used for filling the cells were acquired by the individual NMIs, although in some cases NMIs collaborated to source material in a single purchase.

The cells were designed to be filled with the piston method, where during the last filling a piston is pushed down into the extension that is screwed on to the crucible. The extension allows more metal or metal-carbon mixture to be added during each melt. When the piston is pushed down it helps the cell in filling completely, while any excess will be pressed into the piston and can later be used for analysis of impurities.

The metal used in the project was of a purity of 99.99% or better and came as a powder or in small bits (cubes, cylinders, drops or clippings from a sheet). The carbon used was in powder form and generally about 3% by weight was used. For the eutectic cells the metal and carbon were mixed before it was added to the crucibles. This was in some cases difficult due to the large size difference between the metal bits and the graphite powder, although it did not seem to cause any issues with the melting or with the finished fixed points.

Due to the design with the added extension, it was possible to fill most of the pure metal cells in only one or two melts. When metal in powder form was used it required more melts due to the low density. There was no reports of cell breakage during filling, but there were cases where the extension broke. Additional problems included metal leaking outside the crucible, difficulties removing the extension and incorrect carbon contents in the mixture. The problems related to a stuck extension and piston had to do with the metal alloying itself with the carbon in the graphite, thereby acting as a glue and leading to the extension having to be cut off with a saw. The incorrect carbon contents was in the Pd-C fixed points and resulted in an ingot that had not melted properly and had a dry feel to it. The reason was an excess of carbon, and it resulted in the cells needing to be remade because they did not contain enough of the metal-carbon mixture.

During usage of the fixed points there were some issues, although they mostly worked as expected. A few of the cells have cracked and broken during usage for varying, sometimes unknown reasons. Two Co-C and one Re-C cell had the same issues, with a badly defined melting plateau and an unexpectedly low melting temperature. The metal for all three cells was specified to be 99.99% purity, but it is likely that the problems were caused by impurities. None of the metal in these cells have been sent off for analysis, so it is not yet known for sure if this is the reason and in that case what impurity caused it.

Before the fixed-point cells could be properly used, they had to be optimized in terms of the positioning in the furnace, the ramp speed and the set-points on the furnace. This was done by measuring the temperature gradients in the furnace and positioning the cell where they were as small as possible. The optimal furnace set –points and ramp speed were found by trial and error, where it was changed until the melting plateau was as long and well defined as possible.

7 Appendix

- A. Drawings of graphite parts pdf
- B. HTFP filling procedureV2.pdf